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BIOLOGY AND IMMATURE MORPHOLOGY OF *HEMITELES SIMILIS* (HYMENOPTERA: ICHNEUMONIDAE: CRYPTINAE) PARASITIZING IN EGG COCOONS OF SPIDERS

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Gumovsky, A. V. Biology and immature morphology of *Hemiteles similis* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Cryptinae) parasitizing in egg cocoons of spiders. — The ovipositing behavior and immature morphology of *Hemiteles similis* (Gmelin, 1790), a gregarious egg parasitoid of the garden orbweaver *Araneus diadematus* (Aranei: Araneidae), is observed and described. The female lays eggs externally on the spider eggs within the cocoon. The larvae develop as egg predators and suck the host eggs. Immature stages as well as peculiarities of the parasitoid behavior, are described.

Key words. Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, *Hemiteles similis*, *Araneus diadematus*, egg parasitoids, Europe.

Гумовський, О. В. Біологія та морфологія преімагінальних фаз розвитку *Hemiteles similis* (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae: Срутїнае), що паразитує в яйцевих коконах павуків. — В статті описано спостереження яйцекладної поведінки та морфологію преімагінальних фаз розвитку *Hemiteles similis* (Gmelin, 1790), гregarного паразита яєць павука-хрестовика *Araneus diadematus* (Aranei: Araneidae). Самка відкладає яйця зовні на яйця павуків всередині кокона. Личинки розвиваються як яйцеїди і висмоктують яйця хазяїна. Описано преімагінальні фази, а також особливості поведінки паразитоїдів.

Ключові слова. перетинчастокрилі, Ichneumonidae, *Hemiteles similis*, *Araneus diadematus*, яйцеві паразитоїди, Європа.

Introduction

Despite most insect parasitoids are associated with other insects, some groups attack immature or adult spiders (summarised by Durkin et al., 2021). Apart from the records of the parasitoids of nymphs and adult spiders (e.g., Kloss et al., 2016; Messas et al., 2017), there are many records on the parasitoids reared from spider egg cocoons (e.g., Johnson et al., 2023). These records may indeed concern either primary or secondary parasitoids, or both. So, laboratory experiments followed by detailed observations are needed to clarify the details of the biology of parasitoid species, especially the ones having many host records.

Hemiteles similis (Gmelin, 1790) is one of the species having many host records, and spiders are among them. The purpose of this paper is to describe some biological peculiarities, early development and morphology of immature stages of *H. similis*, as well as experimental establishment of the parasitism of this species on spider hosts.

Material & methods

The spider cocoons were collected in Heteren (Netherlands), in the former campus of the Institute of Ecology of the Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences (NIOO-KNAW) (51.954136, 5.742332), under roofs of constructions in September 2010 (Figs 1A, B). The egg sacks were dissected with a purpose to locate parasitoid immatures. If the parasitoid larvae were found (namely, the penultimate and final instars, and the pupae), they were observed and documented. Then the immature parasitoids were placed back to the cocoons for further development. Three parasitoid females emerged in the beginning of October 2010 and were fed by honey and kept for further experiments.

The mature and fed females of garden orbweaver were collected under the roof and placed in small containers (Figs 1C, D), where they constructed their egg sacks soon afterwards, and died in couple of days. Then the fresh spider egg sacks were proposed to the parasitoid females.

Fig. 1. Collecting of spider cocoons and their parasitoids: A — The author is collecting spider cocoons under the roof of old NIOO buildings (Heteren, Netherlands); B — Cocoons of the garden orbweaver, *Araneus diadematus*, at the window frame; C, D — Plastic containers with spider females and their freshly laid cocoons.

All females were virgin, but nevertheless they started ovipositing in couple of days after eclosion (Fig. 2). The development of the parasitoid was observed in laboratory. The ovipositing behavior of the parasitoid and development of its immatures were documented using imaging facilities. Video and photo recordings were conducted using Canon PowerShot A650IS and Leica cameras, either manually or firmly attached to microscopes. The light microscopy was carried out using the Leica compound microscope connected to digital camera.

Results

The parasitoid, *Hemiteles similis* (Gmelin, 1790)

Hosts. *H. similis* is reported as a parasitoid associated with wide range of hosts, although the most reliable records concern spider egg sacks (Schwarz & Shaw, 2000; here). So, the host records may be subdivided into two groups, reliable records (spiders) and the records,

which require a confirmation and look doubtful in view of the confirmed and described below association with spiders. The spider records concern *Araneus diadematus* (Giraud & Laboulbène, 1877; here), *Arctosa leopardus* (Seyrig, 1927), *Zygiella x-notata* (Perkins & Nixon, 1939; Horstmann, 1970; Schwarz & Shaw, 2000; Quicke & Shaw, 2004).

The doubtful records are more numerous and concern gall wasps *Adleria kollari* (Hymenoptera, Cynipidae) (Fitch, 1880a; Fulmek, 1968), sawfly *Dendrolimus pini* (Hymenoptera, Tenthredinidae) (Dalla Torre, 1902; Komárek & Kolubajiv, 1941); and various lepidopterans: leaf miner (Gracillariidae) *Phyllonorycter spinicolella* (Fitch, 1880b), leafroller (Tortricidae) *Notocelia cynosbatella* (Giraud & Laboulbène, 1877) and *Epinotia nigricana* (Capek, 1961), and even the large white *Pieris brassicae* (Pieridae) (Sedivy, 1986).

Biology. Primary gregarious ectoparasitoid associated with egg sacks of spiders (based on reliable host records; here).

Distribution. Holarctic (Yu et al., 2016).

Fig. 2. A–D — female of *Hemiteles similis* ovipositing into newly laid cocoons of the garden orbweaver (laboratory experiments).

The host, garden orbweaver *Araneus diadematus*

Araneus diadematus is one of the most common spiders found in wide range of habitats (Colebourn, 1974). In early autumn the female lays about 300–900 eggs packed in an egg sack in a shape of a dense silk cocoon (Fig. 1B). The cocoon consists of a hard silk and often has a network of hard silk threads forming a “buffer area” around the cocoon (of about 1.0 cm), separating the cocoon

from surrounding and making it less accessible for natural enemies (Fig. 1B). The exhausted spider female dies soon after the cocoon formation and the young spider nymphs emerge next spring in nature.

Fig. 3. Egg of *Hemiteles similis* on the eggs of the garden orbweaver (cocoon is partly broken for observations). A, C — general view (egg arrowed); B, D — egg enlarged; E — transmitted light microscope image of the egg, scale bar = 0.3 mm.

The parasitoid, *Hemiteles similis*

Ovipositing behaviour of the parasitoid (Fig. 2)

In autumn, the females of *H. similis* start ovipositing shortly after eclosion, at least couple of days after emergence from the host egg sack (cocoon). If the female is proposed a spider cocoon, it starts searching along the cocoon's surface by drumming its surface with her antennae. Then she bends her gaster and tries to puncture the cocoon with her ovipositor (Fig. 2). However, since the external net wall isolates the main cocoon body, it requires her efforts to find an appropriate oviposition place. Apart from the established use of vibration cues for host location (Broad & Quicke, 2000), the female obviously uses chemical cues, since it occasionally tries stinging areas nearby the cocoon, possibly due to chemical marks of spider. Sometimes the female crawls through the web to get closer to the eggs, bending her gaster and poking around (Figs 2A, B). As long as the female has located the cocoon's body, she inserts the tip of the gaster inside and stays nearly immobile what suggests oviposition process. The oviposition may take 1-4 minutes. If a somewhat damaged cocoon (with broken silk coating) is proposed to the parasitoid female, the initial observation takes longer and the female stays nearly immobile between drumming episodes (Fig. 2C). However, in case of intact cocoon, it moves permanently. Then she eventually bends her gaster downwards, erects the ovipositor and stings the egg masses shortly before it eventually finds appropriate place (Figs 2A, B), inserts the ovipositor deeply and starts oviposition (Fig. 2D).

The female lays elongate white eggs sparsely onto the eggs of the spider (Fig. 3). The egg develops relatively long, about a week at room temperature. The newly emerged first instar larva is grub-like, with notable short antennae (Figs 4A–C). It starts feeding by sucking the spider eggs, about a day after hatching. There are normally 3-5 larvae developing inside the spider cocoon, and the siblings do not demonstrate any aggressive behavior to each other. The larva sucks the host eggs, grows slowly and pupates about three weeks later. The damaged host eggs shrink and get darkened. If four parasitoid larvae develop inside the spider cocoon with about 100-150 eggs, then eventually only about ten spider eggs successfully develop into nymphs. Pupation of the parasitoids takes place inside the spider cocoon. The mature larva (Fig. 4F) spins hard dark-brown cocoon, where it pupates soon. The parasitoid cocoons are attached to the silk threads of the host's egg sac. Adults emerge from the spider egg sacs about a month after the maternal oviposition and overwinter as adults (Rasnitsyn, 1964)

Immature stages of parasitoid

Egg. The freshly laid egg is milky in colour (rich of yolk), spindle-shaped, 0.28–0.3 mm long and 0.05–0.06 mm wide, lacks any discernible sculpture in reflected light (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4. Larvae of *Hemiteles similis* in the cocoon of the garden orbweaver. A — general view (larva arrowed); B–C — larva enlarged, scale bar = 0.3 mm; D, E — penultimate and final instars (arrowed in D); F — final instar, habitus, scale bar = 4.0 mm.

First instar. The larva has 13 segments. One spiracle is situated between the I and II (thoracic) segments, and 8 spiracles are situated on each of IV–XI segments (Figs 4A–C, 5). The antenna is papilliform ($l = 0.02$ mm; $w = 0.0067$ mm), with a small sensillum on antennal orbit (Fig. 5).

The labrum is bilobed, with two small setae and two discernible sensilla, ventral zone of labial sclerite is with two setae basally and with symmetrical groups of three sensilla on either side near the margin. The lateral areas of the labrum is with 6 sensilla each. Mandible sickle-shaped, 27 μ m long, its base 17.5 μ m long.

Final instar (Fig. 4F). The newly molted final instar also has 13 body segments and is about 4.0 mm long, 1.5–2.0 mm wide. Its lightly sclerotised mandibles turn darker when the larva is fully grown. The fully-grown larva has dorsal proleg-like swelling with traceable fine structure on each segment and pale inclusions in its darker body.

Fig. 5. First instar larva of *Hemiteles similis*. A, general view; B, head and anterior part of body in lateral view; C, head enlarged.

Pupa. The fully-formed pupa demonstrates all the outlines of the body of adult, likewise in most other ichneumonids. It is pale initially, but darkens quickly. The adult is discernible through transparent teguments of the pupa.

Discussion

The reported observations confirm the association of *H. similis* with spiders, the garden orbweaver *Araneus diadematus* in particular, as a primary gregarious egg ectoparasitoid that develops inside the host egg sac (Figs 4A, B, D, E). The oviposition traits and development of

the parasitoid suggest that many if not all of the reported non-spider host associations listed above, rare doubtful. The tolerance to siblings and the lack of siblicide among the first parasitoid instars support the obligatory gregarious nature of *H. similis* (regardless to the eventual number of adult parasitoids successfully emerged from given cocoon).

The first instar of *H. similis* is characterised by the relatively long antennae (Fig. 5). For example, the antennae of *H. similis* are considerably longer in the first instars of pimpline parasitoids associated with woodwasps (Spradbery, 1970). This may suggest the involvement of such structures in active host search while crawling inside the host egg sack.

The morphology of the final instar of *H. similis* (Fig. 4F) is similar to other ichneumonid parasitoids, especially of spider parasitoids, for example even not closely related pimpline ichneumonids. Gonzaga et al. (2010) mentioned that the final instars of these wasps grasp the lines of the spider orb with their dorsal proleg-like swellings whose tips are covered with minute hooks. The final instar of *H. similis* also has such dorsal structures but their surface is lightly sculptured that likely suggests the lesser contact with the host web, if compared to the members of *Polysphincta* group of genera, which develop in the orb, not in egg sacks.

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